

FP4. LYOTROPIC LIQUID CRYSTALLINE NANOASSEMBLIES: ADVANCED MULTIFUNCTIONAL NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Cancer remains a leading cause of mortality. Despite significant breakthroughs in conventional therapies, treatment remains far from ideal due to high toxicity and therapeutic inefficiency. Current research focuses on the development of multifunctional nanosystems for delivery of different therapeutic agents. Lyotropic liquid crystalline (LLC) mesophases have emerged as a promising class of advanced delivery systems due to the several advantages of highly curved nonlamellar lipid assemblies including a higher surface area to volume ratio. Furthermore, they present structures with variable membrane stress, which is useful for improving permeation and cell internalization.

Given their promising features, we developed and optimized LLC nanoassemblies by considering the different methods of preparation and loading with doxorubicin, as well as their colloidal stability, through comprehensive physicochemical characterization. In addition, we also evaluated the therapeutic efficacy of nanoassemblies by the kinetic drug release profiles, cytotoxicity studies and cellular uptake.

The developed LLC nanoassemblies had a size of less than 250 nm, a high drug encapsulation efficiency (>90%), and a high drug loading capacity (>7%) with a colloidal stability lasting at least 4 weeks. Moreover, the kinetic drug release profiles demonstrated that the produced LLC nanoassemblies reduce cytotoxicity in healthy cells, since the cubosomes showed a higher release of DOX under acidic conditions (pH 5.5, typical of tumor tissues) and a significantly lower release under normal physiological conditions (pH 7.5), which is consistent with cytotoxicity studies and cellular uptake. Overall, these findings suggest that therapeutic agents loaded into LLC nanoassemblies could offer superior improvements to conventional chemotherapy.